

Determination of Rare-Earths and Rare-Elements with Fluoride by an Amperometric Indicator Method

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Amperometric indicator method using two stationary platinum electrodes at constant applied voltage has been used for the determination of rare earths Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy and rare elements Sc and Hf with fluoride in the presence of small amounts of ferric chloride as an indicator. The pH at which rare-earths and rare elements were determined was between 2.5 to 3.0. The percentage error was observed within 1 0%.

SEVERAL¹ electroanalytical techniques have been developed during the past few years for the quantitative estimation of rare-earths and rare-elements. Ringbom and Wilkman² used a small amount of ferric iron as indicator in the estimations of aluminium, magnesium and calcium by fluoride involving precipitation reaction.

This paper reports the results of determination of rare earths and rare-elements with fluoride using two identical polarized platinum electrodes at 50 mV in the presence of small amounts of ferric chloride as an indicator.

Experimental

Rare-earth and rare-element salts used were of B.D.H. or Merck's extra pure quality. The respective nitrates and chlorides of rare-earths and rare-elements were dissolved separately in conductivity water and their contents estimated using standard methods³. Standard potassium fluoride solution used for titration was obtained by appropriate dilution of a strong stock solution which has been standardized potentiometrically⁴. The test solutions were obtained by appropriate dilution of the concentrated stock solutions containing almost the same volume of 95% ethyl alcohol.

Experimental set up and the procedure used in titration is similar to that described by Stone and Scholten⁵. Titrations were carried out in the suitable supporting electrolytes and 0.5 ml of 0.05M ferric chloride was added as indicator. Readings were taken at uniform intervals usually 30 seconds after each addition of titrants. End points were determined graphically by plotting current against volume of the titrant added. A typical titration curve is shown in Fig. 1. For every sample under investigation six iterated determinations were made,

Fig. 1. Amperometric titrations of 0.2885 mg. Neodymium. Using ferric iron as indicator amount observed 0.2880 mg.

Results and Discussion

The titration reaction involving the precipitation of the metallic fluoride is $M^{+n} + nF^{-} \rightarrow MF^n$, where M is the element to be estimated and n its valency. The indicator is the small amount of ferric iron, whose reduction constitutes the indicating system. Up to the equivalence point, current remains constant, after it, ferric ions react with excess fluoride ions and the current falls. The corresponding titration curve has the shape shown in Fig. 1. Addition of an almost equal volume of ethyl alcohol decreases the solubility of the precipitate still further and yield results with improved accuracy especially at higher dilutions. The working conditions are well controlled and the results do not depend on the characteristic of the apparatus used, so the prior calibration is not needed.

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